

The Usage of Virtual Reality in Task-Based Language Teaching

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Experiential learning, in which knowledge acquisition occurs *via* as opposed to *for* task performance, represents a core principle of task-based language education. Against this background, virtual reality (VR) holds the potential to provide incidental learning experiences by facilitating communicative, socio-physical interactions across a host of language learning domains. Thus, it is the purpose of this article to describe the use of VR as a medium for task-based language teaching. Specifically, the capabilities of the Oculus Quest VR headset will be outlined by disclosing the background, implementation, and results of a small-scale study in which tertiary-level English as a foreign language participants utilized VR to navigate the information gap game *Keep Talking and Nobody Explodes*. Key findings indicate that the convergence of VR and commercial game software constitutes engagement that, in keeping with the principles of task-based inquiry, occasions learner collaboration and student-led resolution. More distinct to the VR method, however, is an enhanced sense of presence within its accompanying “world.”

INTRODUCTION

More than 80 years ago, Dewey (1938) reasoned that, as part of a progressive doctrine, education should be experiential, whereby students learn by *doing*. Within the sphere of language education, this core principle of task-based instruction enables the delivery of contextually authentic, student-centered content via incidental learning. Despite the advantages of this socio-constructivist approach, however, Hanson and Shelton (2008) note that it is customary for learners to study within decontextualized environments, and in this vein, language acquisition content may often prove unengaging and lacking in tasks connected directly to the learner’s linguistic or socio-educative needs.

Against this background, virtual reality (VR) technologies hold the potential to reinforce the strengths of task-based language teaching (TBLT) by simulating learning environments that exploit collaboration and existing linguistic knowledge. Further, VR is characterized in terms of “immersive, multisensory experience[s]” (Gigante, 1993, p. 3), requiring the usage of immersive technologies to sustain a simulated user interface. Consequently, VR provides distinct experiences that, in keeping with TBLT, may be perceived as “important, urgent, or meaningful” (Aubrey, 2017, p. 719). Despite these benefits, the nascent status of task-based VR instruction dictates that expansion in terms of viable pedagogy is necessary before

more pervasive adoption may occur.

Through a small-scale account of VR usage within a Japanese English as a foreign language (EFL) context, this article hopes to communicate the qualities that, in the view of the authors, confirm VR as a novel vehicle for task-based language acquisition; one that facilitates contextual, collaborative, and self-determined learning, and uniquely to the medium, a highly immersive synthetic presence. Specifically, the TBLT practice described here utilizes the Oculus series of gamified VR hardware in conjunction with the immersive information gap software *Keep Talking and Nobody Explodes* (KTNE). In demonstrating both the strengths and, where appropriate, limitations inherent to this approach, it is hoped that this enquiry draws attention to a new type of computer-assisted language learning (CALL) that offers encouraging possibilities for future task-based practice.

BACKGROUND

The Rationale for CALL and Task-Based Language Teaching

As noted by Thomas and Reinders (2010), TBLT and CALL share a sequence of conceptual antecedents, comprising “project-based, content-based, and experiential learning, as well as constructivist and social constructivist thought” (p. 5). Lambert (2019) noted that experiential learning within the TBLT context is anchored to three points of reference: learning by doing, individual development, and relevance (pp. 155–156). Regarding the former, TBLT involves learners exploiting and refining existing knowledge in an effort to achieve specific language generation outcomes. Language acquisition is thus viewed as an incidental process occurring in consonance with a learner’s communicative requirements.

TBLT further serves to enhance the learner’s capacity to monitor and assess linguistic productions independently, and to establish internal syllabi to navigate a given context (i.e., individual development). Finally, task relevance refers to the utilization of tasks directly applicable to the communicative requirements of participants and, as noted by Lambert (2019), “their conceptions of what being proficient in a language involves” (p. 155). With these fundamental concepts in mind, the conditions for assessing TBLT correspond with Chapelle’s (2001) criteria for CALL task appropriateness, specifically, the principles of meaning focus, learner fit, and authenticity (p. 55).

On a practical level, TBLT-driven CALL directs learner focus towards the real-world employment of language, exploiting existing schemata to scaffold the language acquisition process collaboratively. Consequently, tasks conforming to this approach take a Vygotskian social constructivist turn, with learning positioned as a “creative process of discovery, expression, and synthesis” (Smith & Kim, 2017, p. 325) in which interaction serves as the primary impetus of meaning. In this regard, CALL activities enhance the affective dimensions of language use which may, in turn, reinforce self-efficacy and the willingness of learners to invest personal resources into task performance (Thomas, 2011).

Defining VR

Huang et al. (2010) noted that past descriptions of VR viewed the technology as any three-dimensional world viewed through, amongst other means, projectors, multiple displays, head-mounted devices, and augmented reality and tracked input devices. More recently, however, a consensus has been reached between Sherman and Craig (2003) and Mikropoulus and Bellou (2006), who have defined the current state of VR accordingly:

1. Virtual worlds that can be created to simulate real and impossible environments.
2. Tracking from controllers, headsets, and so on that provide multisensory interactions.
3. Interactional feedback from vibrations, or cause and effect reactions.
4. A high sense of immersion created from points 1–3.

The Usage of VR in Education

It has been noted by Monahan et al. (2008) that certain VR activities increase the degree and quality of peer-to-peer and student-to-content interactions. This synergy further enhances self-reflection and motivation (Lehtinen et al., 1999) while also broadening communities of practice on both the local and remote levels. In this communal context, students explore and negotiate linguistic features in peer-supported environments that minimize negative affective factors (Garcia-Ruiz et al., 2008).

Further, several studies (e.g., Budianto, 2014; Farivar & Rahimi, 2014) have described educational technologies as benefitting learner autonomy. In the context of VR-driven TBLT, self-determination is an inherent characteristic as learners generate contextual learning processes via the active negotiation and manipulation of virtual environments. Further, Schwienhorst (2002) suggested that VR and autonomy go hand-in-hand given the medium is highly effective in creating learner-centered environments. This follows an inquiry by Feria-Marrugo and Zúñiga-López (2016), who reported not only higher self-efficacy amongst participants but a preference for virtual learning over traditional tasks.

Given its multi-modal nature, VR also serves to balance language acquisition considered both implicit (unconscious) and explicit (selective). In the case of virtual reality learning environments (VRLEs), learners encounter visual, auditory, and tactile stimuli, allowing vocabulary to be absorbed within settings that reinforce the cognitive means of acquisition (Chen, 2016). For example, a three-dimensional representation of an airplane may be “touched” via haptic feedback and “heard” through headphones.

Hanson and Shelton (2008), meanwhile, characterized circumstantial learning occasioned by VR as a sequence of cognitive restructurings, from the representational to the conceptual. In this regard, the manipulation of virtual objects permits learners to independently observe and evaluate the immediate conditions of their input, and thus, witness more clearly the causal relationships between action and result, implying that students generate knowledge more effectively within VRLEs.

Finally, the “immersion” described by Mikropoulus and Bellou (2006)

somewhat understates VR's current status. Indeed, VR may better be described in terms of "presence," which represents a heightened sense of absorption within a virtual space, to the point where the participant believes that they are somatically situated within the learning environment. Accordingly, an inquiry by Repetto et al. (2015) measuring the impact of presence on virtual language acquisition demonstrated an increase in test response accuracy in accordance with the perceived authenticity of the VR setting. As posited by Makowski et al. (2017), improved memory recall may result from heightened concentration within highly immersive contexts, creating more complex cognitive processing during language learning (Chen, 2016).

TASK IMPLEMENTATION

Participants

This study consisted of three Japanese private university students (1 male, 2 female), all of whom were nineteen-year-old international studies majors possessing an EFL comprehension level recognized as intermediate to upper-intermediate (B1–B2) by the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages. All learners had participated in one full semester of tertiary-level English education, during which they were exposed to a mixture of oral communication, extensive reading, and academic writing classes weekly. Of the three, only one participant had previous experience of VR technology, albeit in a non-educational context. Finally, two of the three reported that they participated in electronic gaming regularly, while the remaining student indicated that she enjoyed video games "from time to time."

Hardware and Software

This study utilized the Oculus Rift Quest (ORQ) VR gaming headset, which unlike previous iterations of the Oculus product line, is an all-in-one apparatus that foregoes physical or digital connectivity to external PCs. One of the principal benefits of ORQ, therefore, is the freedom of usage given to the user. The onboard Oculus Insight tracking system translates user feedback into the virtual space, regardless of real-world location or play area boundaries, without the need for external sensors or wires. Further, player input is recorded using dual Oculus Touch controllers that allow the user to pick up, hold, and relinquish virtual objects with intuitive, realistic precision and haptic-kinesthetic feedback (see Oculus Quest, 2019).

To target a collaborative, task-based VR experience, it was decided to employ ORQ in conjunction with the information gap puzzle game KTNE. This software is designed to be played with at least two participants, with the player operating ORQ tasked with disarming procedurally generated bombs. One participant wore the headset (the "defuser"), while two others gave them instructions. The defuser has five minutes, or a maximum of three mistakes, until the bomb explodes, at which point participants change roles.

This defuser is assisted by partner "experts," who communicate the

information necessary for successful completion contained within the bomb defusal manual, a contextually immersive instruction booklet. The modules of each bomb manifest algorithmically, resulting in a myriad of bomb component combinations, and the requirement for KTNE participants to generate linguistic and problem-solving strategies in real time via rapid and accurate information exchange. Accordingly, KTNE serves to enhance the following holistic skills:

- Functioning efficiently and strategically as part of a team.
- Describing, labeling, and communicating visual information.
- Generating questions to elicit feedback.
- Searching specialized EFL text to locate precise instructions.

Task Preparation

Given the complex information-gap nature of KTNE, in which the disarmament of bomb modules necessitates virtual wire cutting, code-breaking, maze negotiation, and password and numbered sequence memorization, it was important that participants were given adequate time to prepare. Prior to task implementation, each learner was briefed on the activity, gave informed consent, and provided with a specialized vocabulary list, module identification chart (see Figure 1), and bomb defusal manual, before being allocated ten minutes to orientate themselves to the task. During this time, the authors prepared a demonstration of the activity to be introduced once students had finished preparation.

FIGURE 1. The Eleven Bomb Module Components Used in KTNE

Post-demonstration, learners were provided with copies of a keypad identification worksheet and given five minutes to translate and label each of the 27 abstract symbols used during the keypad task (see Figure 2). This handout not only facilitated efficient in-game communication of task-critical components but served as a warm-up activity, allowing learners to generate unique and memorable lexical strategies for task completion. This activity conforms to the concepts of supportive performance and focus on form, in which TBLT activities provide learners opportunities to “optimize their own task performance by being provided with time to plan,” and draw attention to “forms that are difficult to acquire incidentally during the performance of communicative tasks,” respectively (Lambert, 2019, p. 156). During the final phase of task preparation, each participant completed the five-minute KTNE tutorial. This level consisted of utilizing the ORQ headset and controllers for basic orientation tasks, such as navigating the virtual space and fundamental task completion measures, including item manipulation, wire cutting, and button pressing.

FIGURE 2. The Various Symbols Used in the KTNE Keypad Activity

Q	Ë	©	б	Ψ	б
A	Q	Ω	¶	¶	Ë
λ	Q	Q	Б	Б	✖
h	Q	Ж	ИЖ	©	æ
ИЖ	☆	¿	Ж	¶	Ψ
κ	κ	λ	¿	Ξ	Й
Q	¿	☆	¶	★	Ω

Task Delivery and Feedback

Initially, participants were divided into a single defuser and two experts, and were tasked with completing KTNE’s five-minute opening level, which involved an elementary device containing three procedurally generated modules (see Figure 3). While the defuser employed the ORQ headset and controllers to navigate the virtual environment, experts were tasked with assisting the defuser using the bomb disposal manual. Learners were directed to proceed throughout the device tiers, with each instance becoming gradually more complex until failure. Due to time constraints, this was limited to three defuser sessions per user, all of which were successful. It should be noted that while this activity initially required players to disarm three modules per device, a single game of KTNE may

incorporate up to eleven, with game time adjustable in increments of 30 seconds to account for the additional complexity of more advanced puzzles. Upon the completion of each bomb defusal session, participants were instructed to swap roles between defuser and expert so each learner could experience the KTNE activity loop in its entirety. All participants were successful in defusing the bomb.

FIGURE 3. The First Bomb, Featuring (Left to Right) Keypad, Button, and Wires Activities

Once all learners had completed three bomb puzzles as a defuser, participant reception and feedback measures were implemented. Specifically, player enjoyment, engagement, and contribution levels were self-reported via a semi-structured group interview, with the task participation and socialization elements that impacted the learning experience grouped under the themes highlighted in this article’s background section. Further, the perceived suitability of the technology for contextual-experiential language generation, and its impact on participant desire to exploit VR media for tertiary-level EFL consumption, was addressed. It should also be noted that participants were encouraged to respond in either Japanese or English, depending on their comfort with the concepts being discussed; the majority of recorded feedback was in English. To ensure thorough thematic evaluation of this data, interview transcripts were analyzed inductively via open coding methods, including Braun and Clark’s (2006) six-phase framework for thematic analysis, which involved examination of the aggregated data set, as opposed to individual participant responses (Rivas, 2012, p. 370).

LEARNER FEEDBACK AND DISCUSSION

As noted by Aubrey (2017), the cognitive mechanisms that drive task-based interactions “involve curiosity-driven engagement with a specific activity, such as solving a problem, which can impact emotional engagement through changes in willingness to interact, attitudes towards the task, and sense of enjoyment” (p. 3). In this vein, findings indicate that VR represents a feasible delivery method for TBLT. Specifically, participants reported a uniformly high degree of satisfaction

with VR, stating that it was “fun” on numerous occasions and that the enjoyable and collaborative nature of the activity acted as a potential driver of interaction and task completion, and reporting that they “didn’t hesitate to talk,” particularly when occupying the role of defuser.

In this regard, the VR task may have involved participants emotionally to build an intrinsically rewarding language learning experience that, in keeping with Csikszentmihályi’s (1990) flow theory, engendered immersion conducive to higher involvement and improved task performance. The heightened degree of co-located collaboration, in which the task was judged to be “especially fun because we got to play it together,” created a sense of shared belonging. This enhanced group social identity, potentially creating a more tangible context for the language being acquired and the conditions that drive learning (Lave & Wenger, 1990).

It should also be noted that the gamified nature of the task at times occasioned incidental linguistic performance (“I really didn’t notice or care about the language”), demonstrating consistency with the learning-by-doing concept that upholds TBLT practice. However, that is not to say that form was eschewed entirely. On several occasions, participants noted that they were careful to verbalize their inquiries clearly when operating within the virtual environment. Interestingly, this was noted to be the most challenging part of the activity on account of the isolating nature of the ORQ apparatus. When asked how this impacted their language usage, one respondent described how they “had to explain things more clearly, and I had to listen more carefully” because the “emotions or face[s]” of her partners were not readily visible.

These statements support a heightened sense of presence experienced by learners within the virtual space and, to some extent, the findings of Repetto et al. (2015), who found a direct correlation between linguistic accuracy and the degree of immersion within a VR environment. The impact of cognitive presence was confirmed by all participants, who agreed that the TBLT experience felt realistic in VR. Moreover, one learner indicated that “[VR] was much better [because] you felt like you were there in that situation.” Further, the presence experienced during collaboration motivated learners to take additional team strategy measures, demonstrating consistency with Garzotto (2007), who lists “apply[ing] knowledge for creative problem solving, develop[ing] strategies for overcoming obstacles, and optimiz[ing] performance within constraints” (p. 29) as key skills for CALL gamification.

While not explicitly directed to do so, it was noted by the authors that the subjects immediately divided the expert role into two distinct phases. Upon the commencement of a new bomb disposal task, the defuser would describe the virtual bomb per the module identification chart, giving a brief overview of each activity to be completed. At the same time, both experts took notes and located pertinent information in the bomb disposal manual before providing instructions on a rotational basis. While Expert 1 was directing the defuser to complete the first module, Expert 2 was researching the next activity and formulating English-medium questions that facilitated efficient task completion. In doing so, the learners adapted their linguistic output, establishing internal strategies to navigate the language generation context of KTNE, suggesting a consistency with the individual development previously described as an essential feature of effective task-based practice.

Additionally, when questioned on their preferred number of participants for task performance, the learners were uniform in their belief that three players facilitated efficient communication and collaboration. Specifically, if the number of experts was to be increased, the complexity of the task would be enhanced unnecessarily on account of the difficulty in tracking additional peer commands and feedback; put simply, “you wouldn’t be sure who to listen to.” Likewise, one expert was viewed as inadequate given that “it would be more difficult to read everything [with] one person,” thereby negatively impacting the process of locating, categorizing, and communicating task-critical information described above. It should be noted, however, that this was the learners’ first time using both ORQ and KTNE, so any frame of reference was severely limited.

Despite agreeing that “[VR] would be a good study thing for the class,” participants were hesitant to give it their full recommendation for tertiary-level EFL education on account of its enjoyability. Specifically, it may be viewed as “more like a game, rather than [something by which] to learn language.” While a valid critique, this statement nevertheless emphasizes the potential for subconscious language acquisition via collaborative gaming software. This is consistent with the findings of Garzotto (2007), who posits that the positive affective considerations occasioned by participating in multiplayer games represent a key motivation for learner engagement, raising educational effectiveness via incidental learning experiences.

Indeed, recognizing the association between learning and social interaction (Rogoff, 1990), the educational benefits of VR are, as noted by Garzotto (2007), “potentially even stronger in situations of social gaming involving multiple players” (p. 29). Following Ellis (2003), the task’s cognitive and interactive demands, and the presence of incidental EFL acquisition, strengthen the authors’ claims of effective task-based practice. Lambert (2019) also notes that TBLT conceptualizes tasks “in terms of learners’ real-world needs and the relevance that this has for them” (p. 14). While the likelihood of these learners participating in legitimate bomb disposal remains extremely remote, successful navigation of the VR task necessitated the use of true-to-life communicative skills, including critical thinking, problem-solving, peer-to-peer negotiation, and the four skills for communication.

The applicability of VR for contextual language learning and holistic skill development is further supported by participant feedback. When questioned, “Do you believe that VR can have a positive impact on your ability to communicate in English?” the learners were uniform in their agreement, clarifying not only that they would like to experience VR EFL content in their future education but that the presence felt during these activities would prove beneficial to their relevant, and thus authentic, language generation contexts. Specifically, one participant noted the difficulty in transferring vocabulary acquired during regular classes to real-world situations; yet, “if I use that word in this [VR] situation, in this class, I can get used to it.”

Limitations and Suggestions for Future Practice

Given its purposefully small-scale nature, this account of VR-driven TBLT lays no claims to comprehensiveness; indeed, considering this study utilized low

participant numbers and was conducted within a single department within a private Japanese university setting, its results are highly contextual. With this in view, the authors advise caution if attempting to generalize these findings beyond their present scope. Nevertheless, Donmoyer (2008) suggests that “reading qualitative accounts of radically different cases could produce enriched cognitive schema ... [which] would allow for a kind of intellectual generalization even when settings are radically different” (p. 372).

Further, the negative impact of COVID-19 on this inquiry cannot be overstated. Follow-up measures were severely impeded and limited to additional questioning only. To that end, the authors suggest that future investigations into task-based VR increase not only student numbers, but the number and variety of devices used. For example, utilizing two or more ORQ units (budget allowing) to increase the number of defuser roles and thus groups actively participating in the task. It was the intention of this study to repeat KTNE sessions while also using tablets or laptops so that comparisons could be made between devices, user interfaces, and learner experiences. The authors had hoped that this would enhance the conclusions of this study and encourage future researchers to develop upon the method described here.

The authors also concede that the novelty effect, or the tendency for task performance to improve primarily in response to curiosity in a newly introduced technology, may have played a role in learner feedback. As previously described, all participants reported little to no previous experience with VR, and none within an educational context. Given that learning gains occasioned by the novelty effect “tend to diminish as students become more familiar with the new medium” (Pisapia et al., 1993, p. 76), it must also be recognized that a more longitudinal strategy would have benefitted this study. Again, this was not possible due to the outbreak of COVID-19; however, the authors hope to implement follow-up measures in a future investigation.

It should also be noted that the technology presented here revealed several practical constraints that necessitate clarification. For instance, despite the increased affordability of the technology, VR gamification remains an expensive endeavor. Presently, the official Oculus website prices ORQ at ¥49,800–62,800, depending on onboard storage capacity (Oculus Quest, 2019). With this expense in mind, the authors speculate that a blended learning station rotation model (Staker & Horn, 2012) may improve the learning experience of larger groups, in which, for example, learners rotate on a fixed schedule between teacher-led instruction, collaborative task-based activities, and VR.

Indeed, the expense and inherently isolating nature of the technology (Keskitalo, 2011) may restrict the implementation of VR within larger groups, particularly during first-time use. It is suggested that practitioner familiarity with the technology and, more importantly, learner-task sequencing and scaffolding are crucial. Additionally, while KTNE is a seated experience offering sufficient multi-modal interactions, it lacks a key presence multiplier, namely standing and navigating the physical space (Chan, 2015). In the context of the present study, this involved a relatively comfortable user experience; however, a significant portion of VR software is comprised of locomotion-based activities (Boletsis & Cedergren, 2019) that may create a disparity with the body’s vestibular system, thereby resulting in nausea and vertigo (Clarke et al., 2016).

It should also be noted that ORQ is not specifically targeted towards pedagogical contexts and thus lacks the classroom management functionality that rival solutions, such as ClassVR (2019), offer as standard. ClassVR provides educators with a host of features, including the capacity to launch activities simultaneously, highlight key areas within a VR application, and display headset views in real time, albeit with significantly inferior tracking capabilities and headset specifications compared to the ORQ. While several of the features offered by ClassVR are feasible in ORQ, they necessitate an advanced knowledge of the apparatus on behalf of the educator if they are to be implemented.

While gamified VR-TBLT represents the core focus of this investigation, it is worth mentioning other pedagogic approaches to the technology. For example, VR presence further supports the understanding of intricate concepts via transactional interaction with immersive multimedia, such as video and real-time satellite imagery. A geography-centric EFL lesson or syllabus may, for instance, exploit Google Earth VR to “transport” learners to distant terrain landforms to acquire and exploit specialized vocabulary to study climate, topography, or other geographical features (He et al., 2016).

To conclude, this account of task-based practice seeks to provide a deeper awareness of the properties that contribute to the pedagogical application of VR and, in doing so, foster increased adoption within the EFL context. As demonstrated here, the implementation of VR should place functionally relevant educational content as a key driver of the gamified experience. Indeed, the act of play “should draw directly on the knowledge and skills that the game is designed to foster in its users and should promote reflection about or application of such knowledge and skills” (Garzotto, 2007, p. 30) to occasion learning that serves to enhance student interest and enrich the language learning experience. Practitioners may thus apply VR broadly to EFL or English-medium instruction, either as an isolated learning experience or in partnership with traditional classroom methods.

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